

THE FUTURE UNIVERSITIES-SOCIETY COLLABORATION: A SOCIETAL KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT ALTERNATIVES

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Abstract

This paper considers the growing globalized knowledge economy by exploring a complex phenomenon of universities and society collaboration from the perspective societal knowledge management (SKM). There has been substantial research undertaken on the role of knowledge in economic and socio-political agenda. However, researchers have not treated the role of SKM in much detail. The design of this sequential exploratory research is based on an in-depth interview and Focus Group Discussion of four faculty members from four universities and six staffs from local governmental agencies in Pamekasan regency, Indonesia. We analyse the potential knowledge collaborations between universities-society by putting Sistem Inovasi Daerah (SIDA). The findings indicated that there was a positive relationship between universities-society collaboration in the knowledge economy context. The results indicate that SKM profound the ancillary benefit of collaborative engagement in the current landscape of societal workforce. In addition, there is a need to develop an acceptable framework that systematically empower collaborative knowledge management in universities. However, the discussion of SIDA in Pamekasan regency tends to focus on the bureaucratic level, which is unacceptable in academic context that remains at theoretical level. The findings represent a further step towards development of sustainable universities-society collaboration framework.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the current shape of globalized knowledge economy, every nation has seen increased attention to the societal knowledge management (SKM) towards university-society collaboration. At the same time, as the modern society seek progress and success to deal with constant flux, there is widespread recognition of the importance of discussion on the aspect of knowledge management (KM) in current landscape of university as a social institution. On the subject of governance, it has been widely known that university is always been challenged by societal demands for better responsibilities (Brennan, 2012). Societal Knowledge Management in the context of globalized knowledge economy is multifaceted. Although the foundation of SKM is similar with private sector of KM, the principles of SKM is to support and advance societal intents and objectives (Wiig, 2007). In a world where the production and transmission of knowledge become easier through ICT development, it is important to see the growing globalized knowledge economy by exploring a complex phenomenon of universities-society collaboration from different perspective and theoretical background.

Given the complex phenomenon fostering the modern society, nations around the world has been struggling by the potential usage of knowledge in every sphere of lives (Lytras et al., 2009). In a response to this phenomenon, Sistem Inovasi Daerah (SIDA) has been initiated by Indonesia government to enhance a strategic development plan in social and economy at regional basis since 2012. This innovation framework, however, much vaguer to define in academic context. As has already been noted, societal demands will definitely change the role of university.

Following the increasing discussion on university-society collaboration in the knowledge society is the complexity of determinants (Bolling and Erickson, 2016; Fiaz, 2013). The extent to which knowledge management plays a role in university-society collaboration is the adoption of governmental measurements (Bektaş & Tayaouva, 2013; Saleh and Omar, 2013; Nancy and Zach, 2014). Therefore, this paper aims to comprehensively examine the role of SKM in universities-society collaboration in globalized knowledge economy context.

2. METHOD

This design of this paper used sequential exploration with qualitative approach. Finding is based on in-depth interviews with four faculty members from 4 universities and 6 staffs from government agencies in Pamekasan regency, Indonesia. In the data, collection was done focus group discussion (FGD) to reinforce the findings of the existing data in the field in order to develop regional innovation systems in Pamekasan. These studies take a critical standpoint to question assumptions within the framework of the existing SIDA. It aims to explicitly analyze the potential of knowledge-based collaboration between university-society by putting SIDA development framework and the principles of social knowledge management.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A number of trends can be discerned in the recent discussion of university-society collaboration mainly focused on the importance of partnerships, which is leveraging the governance and management of knowledge with other organizations (Brennan, 2012; Jang, 2013). It is a tendency to believe that, in the globalized knowledge economy, university has its role in the validation and accreditation of knowledge. However, the question remain is, will the longevity of recognizable form of university successfully defining its society? Who is responsible to manage university-society collaboration?

There has been substantial research undertaken on the role of knowledge in the global economic and socio-political agenda. However, researchers have not treated the role of SKM in much detail (see e.g. Käpylä, 2012; Sampangi et al., 2012). A large part of research on knowledge management towards university-society collaboration lacks clarity regarding the construction of measurements (see e.g. Bolling and Erickson, 2016; Gardner et al., 2010). What can be agreed, however, is a positive relationship between universities-society collaboration in knowledge economy context. This is an unsurprising result.

Figure 1. SIDA Collaborative Network

Our proposed model of collaboration extends that SIDA's elements by involving network as a tool of collaboration (Figure 1). Three core elements in SIDA profoundly see knowledge as object (KaO) as recallable mental objects that can be communicated on demand (i.e. books, documents, embedded software and hardware). The results of this study indicate that SKM profound the ancillary benefit of collaborative networking in the current landscape of societal workforce. However, focus needs to be shifted from mainly discussing university's role in the knowledge society. SIDA accommodates the networks as important aspect of university-society collaboration, which always been an issue in the previous research (see e.g. Bolling & Erickson, 2016; Jang, 2013). Based on the data analysis, we proposed two types of collaboration. First, substantive collaboration, this collaboration includes government role as supervisor and responsible actor in the collaboration for the innovations. Second, facilitative collaboration, it includes human resource, information technology, and fund policies in the continuation of the collaboration. What remain unclear is how to organize these types of collaboration. Therefore, there is a need to develop an acceptable framework that systematically empower collaborative knowledge management between university and society.

4. CONCLUSION

The findings represent a further step towards development of sustainable universities-society collaboration through SIDA framework. This paper can be used as a base for conceptualizing further responsibility in collaborative knowledge management towards sustainable development at national level. However, the discussion of SIDA in Pamekasan regency tends to focus on the bureaucratic level, which is unacceptable in academic context that remains at theoretical level.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bektaş Ç and Tayauova G 2014 A Model Suggestion for Improving the Efficiency of Higher Education: University-Industry Cooperation *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 116 2270-2277 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.01.558>
- [2] Bölling M and Eriksson Y 2016 Collaboration with Society: The future role of universities? Identifying Challenges for Evaluation. *Research Evaluation* 25(2) 209-218 <https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvv043>

- [3] Brennan J 2012 Is There a Future for Higher Education Institutions in the Knowledge Society? *European Review* 20(2) 195–202 <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1062798711000421>
- [4] Fiaz M 2013 An empirical Study of University–Industry R&D Collaboration in China: Implications for Technology in Society *Technology in Society* 35(3) 191–202 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2013.03.005>
- [5] Gardner P L, Fong A Y, and Huang R L 2010 Measuring the Impact of Knowledge Transfer from Public Research Organisations: A Comparison of Metrics used Around the World *International Journal of Learning and Intellectual Capital* 7 318–27
- [6] Käpylä J 2012 Towards a Critical Societal Knowledge Management *Journal of Intellectual Capital* 13(3) 288–304 <https://doi.org/10.1108/14691931211248873>
- [7] Salleh M S, and Omar M Z 2013 University-Industry Collaboration Models in Malaysia *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 102 654–664 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.10.784>
- [8] Yulong Li, Monideepa Tarafdar, and S Subba Rao 2012 Collaborative Knowledge Management Practices: Theoretical Development and Empirical Analysis *International Journal of Operations & Production Management* 32(4) 398–422 <https://doi.org/10.1108/01443571211223077>
- [9] Wiig K M 2007 Effective Societal Knowledge Management *Journal of Knowledge Management* 11 (5) 141–156 <https://doi.org/10.1108/13673270710819861>

